

FATIGUE BEHAVIOR OF CARBON FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC AND THERMOSET POLYMER COMPOSITES (I) $[\pm 45]_4s$ LAMINATES UNDER TENSION-TENSION LOADING

C.C.M.MA*+, S.H.LIN*, N.H.TAI[†], J.F.WU* and G.Y.WU*
C.L.ONG**, Y.C.CHANG**, M.F. SHEU** and Y.R.YANG[†]

*INSTITUTE OF CHEMICAL ENGINEERING
[†]MATERIALS SCIENCE CENTER
NATIONAL TSING HUA UNIVERSITY
**AERO INDUSTRY DEVELOPMENT CENTER
CHUNG SHAN INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY
HSIN-CHU, TAIWAN, R.O.C.

ABSTRACT

Fatigue behavior of both thermoplastic and thermoset matrix of carbon fiber reinforced laminated composite have been investigated. The $[\pm 45]_4s$ laminates of AS-4/PEEK and T300/976 Epoxy were utilized. The static tensile measurement and tension-tension fatigue loading tests at various levels of stress amplitude were investigated. The median rank method was applied to predict the statistical probability of experimental data of fatigue life under different stress amplitude tests. The S-N curves of various loading frequencies were established using the pooled Weibull distribution function. The theoretical prediction methods could be applied to illustrate the fatigue behavior of both thermoplastic and thermoset matrix polymer laminated composites. Furthermore, both the stiffness degradation and the thermal stress history during fatigue life test are discussed in this study.

INTRODUCTION

The types of matrix used for polymer composites include thermoset and thermoplastic. Due to the elasticity of thermoplastic polymer, the polymer chain will be re-oriented, and causing elongation, under stress loading. In contrast, thermoset polymer exhibits little deformation during loading, due to its chain contracted in crosslinked form⁽¹⁾.

Polymeric materials show a temperature increase under cyclic loading due to the internal friction and viscoelastic process⁽²⁾. There are many factors that affect the temperature increase

*+ To whom all correspondence should be addressed

during fatigue test. Among these factors, both loading condition and test frequency determine the amount of heat generation⁽²⁾. Therefore, such thermal effect might be responsible for the reduction of fatigue strength⁽³⁾.

The objective of this research is intended to study the fatigue life response of [+45]_{4S} T300/976 Epoxy and AS-4/PEEK laminate composite systems at several different stress amplitudes under the three different frequencies, 1 Hz, 5 Hz and 10 Hz. The surface temperature change of the specimen during fatigue test was monitored by thermocouple. The characteristics of fatigue life of laminate subjected to the stress from low cyclic loads to high cyclic loads were investigated. The experimental data were estimated and analyzed by the median rank order-static cumulative-distribution function and the Weibull distribution function, respectively. In this study, the S-N curves at different survival probabilities were presented. Moreover, the change of stiffness during fatigue test was also discussed to explain the damage process.

EXPERIMENTAL

The AS-4/PEEK (APC-2) and T300/976 Epoxy (HYE-1076E) unidirectional prepreps with a thickness of 0.125 mm were purchased from the Imperial Chemical Industry (I.C.I.). U.K. The stacking sequence of laminate was [+45]_{4S} of 16 plies prepreg with a nominal fiber content of 60% vol. in APC-2 or 63% vol. in HYE-1076E, its thickness was 2 mm. All fatigue tests were conducted by using a MTS 810.22 servo-hydraulic test machine under load control mode. Stroke control was employed for static test with a stroke rate of 2 mm/min. Fatigue tests were conducted in room temperature with constant amplitude, tension-tension triangular load cycles. Fatigue stiffness was recorded by using a computerized data acquiring system, including strain gauge, A/D converter, type 759 software developed by MTS Co. Meanwhile, the surface temperature of testing specimen was measured by using a digital type thermocouple detector.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tension-Tension Fatigue Life and Reliability

In fatigue test, 1 Hz, 5 Hz and 10 Hz frequencies were selected for comparing their fatigue behavior. As the two parameters, $\hat{\alpha}_f$ shape parameter and the \hat{N}_0 characteristic life, of Weibull distribution function were obtained, and the fatigue life distribution could then be analyzed. Figures 1 to 3 show the analyzed Weibull distribution curve of fatigue life under different cyclic stress levels.

Figure 4 shows the normalized data and the pooled Weibull distribution at various frequencies. The correlation between the normalized experimental data and the pooled Weibull distribution is excellent. Figures 5 to 7 show the pooled Weibull distribution curve of fatigue life under different cyclic stress levels.

Figure 8 shows the S-N₀ curves at various frequencies. From the figure one can find that a trend of two-segment straight line curve was fitted visually. Experimental results in this study

show that fatigue life is longer for higher frequency. This can be explained by the creep phenomenon, where the specimen remains for longer times below the mean stress at the lower frequencies⁽⁴⁾. Furthermore, at low stress level, the difference of the fatigue life between various frequencies is more significant.

Mechanism and Effect of Temperature Increase

The temperature increasing can be attributed to the internal friction and the viscoelastic nature of the matrix materials. During the fatigue test, $[\pm 45]_4S$ T300/976 Epoxy laminate induces serious damages, such as $+45^0$ surface crack, delamination and fiber fracture. The induction of the apparent temperature increase also can be seen. Figure 9 shows the change of surface temperature of $[\pm 45]_4S$ T300/976 Epoxy laminate at various stress levels under fatigue loading procedure.

In this study, the thermoplastic based carbon fiber reinforced composite, AS-4/PEEK, $[\pm 45]_4S$ laminate exhibits more dramatic variety. AS-4/PEEK demonstrates a significantly larger hysteresis loop in comparing with T300/976 Epoxy, as illustrated in Figure 10. The enveloped area size of hysteresis loop is an indicator of the energy releasing amount during fatigue test. Therefore, AS-4/PEEK was expected to show higher surface temperature than T300/976 Epoxy, as can be seen in Figure 11.

Fatigue Stiffness Change and Failure Mechanisms

Four transient regions of fatigue stiffness were observed during fatigue loading history. In comparison, AS-4/PEEK has more significant effect than T300/976 Epoxy, as shown in Figure 12.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The pooled Weibull distribution function of fatigue life could be applied to the thermoset, Epoxy, based carbon fiber reinforced $[\pm 45]_4S$ laminated under 1 Hz, 5 Hz and 10 Hz tension-tension fatigue loading.
2. The S-N curve of T300/976 Epoxy $[\pm 45]_4S$ laminates shows two segment curve. Due to the creep effect, specimen possesses shorter fatigue life at lower frequency and higher stress level.
3. The surface temperature changing of T300/976 Epoxy $[\pm 45]_4S$ could be classified by 3 modes, that dependent on the applied stress. AS-4/PEEK exhibits higher surface temperature in comparing with T300/976 Epoxy during fatigue test.
4. The fatigue stiffness shows four transient regions during fatigue loading process. By investigating the fatigue stiffness changing history, the failure mechanism of $[\pm 45]_4S$ laminate was confirmed.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This research was supported by the National Science Council of the Republic of China, under the Contract No. NSC-83-0405-D-007-05.

REFERENCES

1. David J. Williams, *Polymer Science and Engineering*, 193-224.
2. H. Neubert, H. Harig and K. Schutle, *Sixth International Conference on Composite Materials and Second European Conference on Composite Materials (ICCM and ECCM)*, 1, 1.359-1.368 (1987).
3. D. C. Curtis, D. R. Moore, B. Slater and N. Zahlan, *Journal of Composite Materials*, 19, 446-452 (1988).
4. A. Rotem and Z. Hashin, *J. of Composite Materials*, 9, 191-206 (1975)

Figure 01 : Comparison Between the Theoretical Prediction Curve and Experiment Data of the Fatigue Life of T300/976 [+45]_{2s} Laminated Composites under 1 Hz Test .

Figure 02 : Comparison Between the Theoretical Prediction Curve and Experiment Data of the Fatigue Life of T300/976 [+45]_{2s} Laminated Composites under 5 Hz Test.

Figure 03 : Comparison Between the Theoretical Prediction Curve and Experiment Data of the Fatigue Life of T300/976 [-45]_{4s} Laminated Composites under 10 Hz Test.

Figure 04 : Comparison Between the Normalized Data and Pooled Two-Parameter Weibull Distribution of T300/976 [+45]_{4s} Laminated Composites at Various Frequencies Fatigue Testing.

Figure 05 : Comparison Between the Pooled Weibull Theoretical Prediction Curves and Experimental Data of the Fatigue Life of T300/976 [+45]_{2s} Laminated Composites at 1 Hz Fatigue Testing.

Figure 06 : Comparison Between the Pooled Weibull Theoretical Prediction Curves and Experimental Data of the Fatigue Life of T300/976 [+45]_{2S} Laminated Composites at 5 Hz Fatigue Testing .

Figure 07 : Comparison Between the Pooled Weibull Theoretical Prediction Curves and Experimental Data of the Fatigue Life of T300/976 [+45]_{2S} Laminated Composites at 10 Hz Fatigue Testing .

Figure 08 : Fatigue S-N₀ Curve of C.F/Epoxy T300/976 [+45]_{4S} Laminated Composite Under Various Frequencies Tension-Tension Loading.

Figure 09 :Surface Temperature of C.F./Epoxy T300/976 [+45]_{4S} Laminates at Various Loading Stresses under 10 Hz Tension-Tension Fatigue Testing.

Figure 10 : Comparison Between the Hysteresis Loop of Gr/PEEK and Gr/Epoxy [+45]_{4S} Laminated Composite under Tension-Tension Loading (124 MPa) after 1,500 Fatigue cycles.

Figure 11 : Surface Temperature Change VS. Fatigue Cycles of AS-4/PEEK and T300/976 Epoxy $[\pm 45]_{4s}$ Laminated Composites at 10 Hz Tension-Tension Fatigue Testing.

Figure 12 : Comparison Between the Fatigue Stiffness of Gr/PEEK and Gr/Epoxy $[\pm 45]_{4s}$ Laminated Composites under Tension-Tension Loading.